

Forestry and Forest Products in Ethiopia

Technologies and Issues

Edited by

**Wubalem Tadesse
Getachew Desalegn
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Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research

Forestry and Forest Products In Ethiopia

Technologies and Issues

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Estimation of Variability for some Morphological Traits and Seed Oil Content in Local Physic Nut Population in Eastern Amhara Region

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Introduction

Ethiopia is characterized by varying environments within a small area, which enables various plant species to evolve. There are hundreds of oil-bearing plant species (Seegler, 1983; Getinet and Nigussie, 1997). These include Niger seed, rapeseed, linseed, sunflower, safflower, castor bean, and sesame, which have either their origin or their centre of diversity in Ethiopia. In addition, there are tree species such as palm, physic nut, castor oil desert date and others that bear oil in their fruit and kernel. Of the oil-seed-bearing tree species, physic nut (*Jatropha curcas* L.) is one of the important species that bear seed containing oil with a potential use as biodiesel.

J. curcas L. (Tropical physic nut) belongs to the family *Euphorbiaceae* and genus *Jatropha*. It is native of tropical America probably Mexico and now found throughout the tropics (Ginwal *et al.*, 2004). It lives for up to 50 years, and grows mostly on marginal soils (Henning, 1996). It is a drought-resistant, multipurpose shrub (tree) species, which can reach a height of up to 5 m. It is commonly known as tropical physic nut and locally (in Ethiopia) as 'Qachima', 'Ayderke', or 'Kermo Ayderke'. Physic nut is now attracting attention as a source of biodiesel, because of its ability to grow on marginal land (Benge, 2006).

Physic nut is a very prominent and widely commended species with a wide variety of uses. In a country such as Mali, it grows mostly as hedges or live-fences, and protects farms from livestock and reduces water and wind erosion (World Bank, 2002). Locally, women use it as a source of raw material for local soap production, and for medicinal purposes such as wound disinfection, as a purgative, for rheumatism, skin disease, etc. It is also used as a bio-pesticide and molluscicide (Duke, 1983). Above all, its seeds contain about

25–42% of non-edible oil that can be used as a diesel substitute (Jones and Miller, 1992). The oil can also be used for a range of other applications such as lubrication and in the manufacture of soap. The seedcake left after oil extraction is toxic for anilan feed. However, it could be used as fertilizer (Heller, 1996).

Physic nut grows in various parts of Ethiopia, as a hedge around homesteads and farmlands, such as in Wolayita, Metekel, Southern Wollo, northern and Eastern Shewa, Gamo Gofa zones and Gambella region. The local land race of *J. curcas* is adapted for the local environmental and socioeconomic condition indicating the potential of the commercial production. This suggests either that physic nut can be cultivated as large-scale plantations on marginal areas, as small-scale hedges, or intercropped to assist rural livelihoods.

Although physic nut already exists in many places in Ethiopia, its economic importance is far from being realized, owing to technical, economic, cultural, and institutional factors. There is little field experience and documented information about the local population of *J. curcas* of Ethiopia.

Currently, Ethiopia has developed a bio fuel strategy to produce renewable energy source through the cultivation of non-edible vegetable oils, primarily from castor bean and physic nut (Ministry of Mines and Energy, 2007). So far, six foreign and local companies have secured land to be used to grow *Jatropha* and palm tree in different regions and the ministry has identified 24 million hectares of land suitable to grow *Jatropha* and palm tree in six regional states (Ministry of Mines and Energy, 2007). This indicates the need to undergo scientific research and development prior to a large scale planting is required for every local area.

The variation in different characters (traits) of *J. curcas* is frequently mentioned in different papers (Heller, 1996; Ginwal *et al.*, 2004; Thongbai *et al.*, 2006; Benge, 2006). For instance, in Jones and Miller (1992) the seed yield reported to vary from 0.4 ton⁻¹ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ to over 12 ton⁻¹ha⁻¹year⁻¹. Again according to Kaushik *et al.* (2007), the oil content of among different accessions collected from different regions of India proved that there is a significant difference in oil content between the accessions, ranging from 28% to 38% of the seed by weight. Again, there is variability in palatability or edibility among the different varieties or population of *J. curcas*. Makkar *et al.* (2002) had reported that there are varieties of *J. curcas* that are edible. In addition, variability in other morphological traits like number of branches per

tree, seed weight, seed size and other growth traits of physic nut were reported (Heller, 1996; Ginwal *et al.*, 2004; Kaushik *et al.*, 2007).

The variation in physic nut population may arise from genetic and/or environmental factor. A considerable genetic variation in growth, chemical composition of seed and seed traits at the level of provenance, variety, or progeny can be expected particularly in out-crossing species such as many species of *Albizia*, *Jatropha*, *Acacia*, and *Prosopis*, which are widely used in agroforestry systems throughout the worldwide landscapes (Kaushik *et al.*, 2007).

On the otherhand, variation in physic nut population could occur because of its adaptability to over a wide range of rainfall, temperature, and soil types. In central India, variation in physic nut was found mainly due to environment and selection pressure (Ginwal *et al.*, 2004). Populations might have experienced marked differences in selective pressure (Sunil *et al.*, 2007).

Variation in any plant species is useful as a source of future genetic selection provided the desired ideo types for intended purpose of utilization. Development of high-yielding varieties requires a thorough knowledge of the existing genetic variation for yield and its components (Wani and Khan, 2006). So the extent and nature of the variability in genetic, agronomic, physiological traits of physic nut should be quantified for maximum utilization of its genetic potential. This indicates the importance of estimating the variation within the existing local population for yield and yield components investigated prior to investing on large plantation.

Physic nut is an introduced species in Ethiopia, although there is no concerted evidence from where, and when, it was introduced. Since the time and point of introduction of physic nut are not known, it is possible that different gene pools were introduced into Ethiopia at different times. In addition to unclear genetic background of local *J. curcas* population, the diverse agro-ecological regions, and climatic conditions of Ethiopia is expected to offer a good opportunity for variability within the population of *J. curcas* in the country.

So far, nothing has done in Ethiopia, on the understanding and improving the genetic aspects of this species. Systematic evaluation on the yield performance of *J. curcas* from different locations has not yet been carried out in the country and to the necessary extent in the other part of the world. Estimating this

variation within the local population of *J. curcas* has paramount importance for initiating a tree improvement program in the country.

Therefore, the main objective of the present study was to estimate the variability in tree morphological traits, seed traits and oil content of local physic nut population in six different sites of Eastern Amhara Region.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

The study was conducted in eastern Amhara Region, where physic nut is found abundantly. The study area lies between 10°00'–11°26' North latitude and 39°46'–40°25' East longitude. The area extends from Showa Robit town (Semen Showa Zone) up to Kemise town (Oromiya Zone). Physic nut is specifically found from Shewa Robit to Harbu Kebele, along the main road that stretches from Addis Ababa to Adigrat and then bends towards Bati along the main road to Semera.

In this study area, there are three administrative Zones: South Wollo, North Shewa, and Oromia Zones of Amhara Regional State. The extent of coverage of the study varies, depending on the criteria of the study. Among 18 plots in the study, one site was in Kewet Woreda of Semen Shewa Zone, specifically in Showa Robit Kebele. There were four sites (three plots per site) in four Woredas of Oromiya Zone, namely Jile-Timuga, Artuma Fursi, Dawa Chefa (Kemise) and Bati Woreda. The specific locations were Senbete, Chefa Robit, Kemise, and Bati Kebele, respectively. The last site was in the South Wollo Zone of Kalu Woreda in Harbu Kebele.

The altitude of the Zone ranges between 600 and 3000 m and comprises three agroclimatic zones: *dega*, *weyna dega* and *kolla*, which account for about 2.6%, 26.2% and 71.2% of the area of the zone, respectively.

Rainfall data at meteorological stations of Bati (1660 m a.s.l.), Kemise (1450 m a.s.l.) and Artuma (1920 m a.s.l.) indicated that the zone receives major rains in summer, preceded by a small rainfall peak in spring or by a prolonged period of moderate rainfall. The long-term (20 years for Bati and 15 years for both Kemise and Artuma) mean annual rainfall was 851 mm, 1035 mm and 1425 mm, respectively (Degefa, 2001). This means that, despite its higher

altitude, Bati has a lower rainfall than Kemise, which is partly explained by the difference relative to the moisture-bearing winds. The temperature in Oromiya Zone decreases sharply from the top of the escarpment in the west to the floor of the Rift Valley in the east. About seven thermal belts exist in the zone, and the mean temperature during the growing seasons ranges 10 °C–27.5 °C (Degefa, 2001).

According to MOA/FAO (1984), six major soil associations cover the landscape of the Oromiya Zone. These are Lithosols, Eutric Cambisols (Lithic), Eutric Cambisols (stony), Eutric Regosols (Lithic), Chromic Vertisols and Orthic Solonchaks. Four sites were selected and established in different parts of the zone. These were Senbete, Chefa Robit, Kemise, and Bati, with 12 plots.

The third zone was South Wollo, which is one of the ten Zones in the Ethiopian Amhara Region. It is bordered on the south by North Shewa and the Oromia Region, on the west by West Gojjam, on the northwest by South Gondar, on the north by North Wollo and on the east by the Oromia Zone. Its highest point is Mount Amba Ferit. Kalu is one of the 105 woredas in the Amhara Region of Ethiopia, and it is part of the South Wollo Zone. Towns in Kalu include Ancharo, Degaga, and Harbu. The altitude of this Woreda ranges from 800 m a.s.l. in the lowlands bordering the Afar Region, to 1,750 m a.s.l. at the foot of the mountains north of Kombolcha. The climate of Kalu varies from dry sub-humid to semi-arid. Important rivers include the Cheleleka and Borkana.

Data Collection

One-hundred and sixty-two trees, making 18 families, were taken for recording of tree and seed traits and oil content. A random branch count and capsule count from each of the sample trees were made directly in the field, after supplementary data, *e.g.* DSH (diameter at stump height \cong 0.1 m) and height were gathered. A sample of one kg of seed was collected from all fertile branches of each sample tree, for recording of seed data and oil content (Kaushik *et al.*, 2007).

The geographical location and elevation were determined by direct personal observation, using a Garmin GPS 76. Meteorological data for each site were gathered from Kombolcha meteorology sub-center of Ethiopian Meteorology Agency. The soil-type information was collected from secondary sources, such as reports from various institutions, the Woreda, and interviews with experts.

A graduated measuring stick and caliper were used to measure a sample describing data; these were height and DSH of the sample tree, respectively.

The tree morphological traits data were gathered, first by counting the branch and capsule on the sample trees in the field to compute the value of number of branch per tree, number of capsule per tree and number of seed per tree following a randomized branch sampling method of Jessen (1955).

The seed size traits were the second type of traits determined in the laboratory. First, the sample seeds were separated from the capsules through manual threshing. The seed size traits, namely seed length, seed breadth and seed thickness or width were measured from the seed sample of each unit. Five samples were drawn from each seed sack, and measured for length, width, and thickness (mm) with a caliper. Sampling of seeds from each sample bag from a particular individual was conducted according to the procedure used by Kaushik *et al.* (2007).

For seed weight, five samples of seed, of 100 seeds each, were taken from each seed lot and weighed in gram ($\pm 10\text{mg}$) on a digital balance in the laboratory, and as for Kaushik *et al.* (2007), all samples of seed were dried under similar temperature and humidity conditions until no change in weight of the seed is observed. As for seed size traits, five randomly drawn samples of seeds from each sample were used to measure the above characters, and averaged to give the specific value of these traits.

The oil content of moisture-free seed was measured by means of magnetic resonance spectroscopy, at Holleta Agricultural Research Center (HARC). Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) is the preferred method, as it is non-destructive (Getinet *et al.*, 2008), and can reduce the error that potentially is induced by the efficacy of the extraction process.

Flowering in *Jatropha* occurs at the end of the rainy season. After two to four months, the capsules tend to mature and become ready for harvesting (Jones and Miller, 1992). The data were collected in December 2007, which was within the limits of the maturity period, as assessed from information gathered about flowering, before data collection.

Secondary data about the sample site were obtained through personal observation or by direct measurement and secondary sources. These background data include geographical location, elevation, climate, and soil

type. In addition, descriptive data on sample trees like tree height and diameter at stump height were gathered.

A count of branch numbers, capsule and seed numbers was made on each of the selected sample trees. The number of branches per tree, number of capsule per tree and number of seeds per tree were determined in the field. These tree traits were considered as tree morphological traits, which determine the overall seed yield per tree, as well as per hectare (Heller, 1996).

Seed size traits (seed length, seed breadth and seed thickness), seed weight traits (single-seed weight and 100-seed weight), and oil content were measured in the laboratory for each lot of sample seeds from a given individual.

Data analysis

The data of each trait were tested for normality and homogeneity. However, the data on tree morphological traits failed to satisfy the assumption of homogeneity of variance, hence were transformed by the square-root transformation. ANOVA was performed, using the one-way procedure, and a test of significance was made by the least significant difference method (LSD), between and within the families (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Physic nut is cross-pollinating species, and comparisons should be made within families rather than lines or single trees (Heller, 1996). This allows the variation within families to be minimized, and maximized among families (Zobel and Talbert, 1984). In the present study, the assumption was that trees exhibit high similarity than with individuals that are within the family or plot, rather than with those outside. Each plot of the 6 sites was considered as a unique genotype or family, and used to estimate genetic variation across the population. Then, a mean comparison of families was performed, by the least significant difference method. For the ANOVA and LSD, Minitab 13 for Windows was used (Minitab, 2000).

First, the partitioning of the total phenotypic variances was done for a single-trait analysis, using a simple model suggested by Kumar *et al.* (2006):

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + f_i + e_{ij} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where, Y_{ij} is the phenotypic value for the j^{th} individual in the i^{th} sample family for a given trait; μ is the general mean; f_i is the random effect of i^{th} family; e_{ij}

is the random within-family effect (i.e. residual error resulting from segregation, dominance, and environmental contributions).

Variances of the phenotypic, genotypic, and environmental components were then estimated according to the method of Kung and Bey (1978). The expected mean squares were used to estimate each component of variance, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Equations for components variances estimation

Components	MS	EMS	variances formula
Genetic	MS_f	$V_e + rV_g$	$V_g = \frac{MS_f - V_e}{r}$
Error	MS_e	V_e	$V_e = MS_e$

Where, MS_f is Mean square among families, MS_e is Mean square within families, V_g is genotypic variance, V_e is environmental or error variance and r is replication.

The coefficients of variation for genotypic (GCV) and phenotypic components (PCV) were then estimated from their respective standard deviations, using the following two equations, according to the method of Mahadevan, *et al.* (1999);

$$GCV = \frac{(\sigma_g^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Mean} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$PCV = \frac{(\sigma_p^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Mean} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Where, σ_g^2 is a genotypic variances and σ_p^2 is a phenotypic variances.

The family broad-sense heritability (h^2) of each trait was estimated from the F -value according to the following formula (Kung and Bey, 1978),

$$h^2 = 1 - \frac{1}{F} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

The responses to selection of the local population investigated were determined using genetic advance (GA) and genetic advance as percentage of mean (GAM). The expected genetic advance (GA) for each character (at 5%

selection intensity) was computed using equation that was suggested by Johnson *et al.* (1955).

$$GA = i \times h^2 \times \sigma_p \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Where, i is constant selection differential ($i = 2.056$) at 5% selection intensity, σ_p is phenotypic standard deviation on mean basis, and h^2 is heritability in the broad sense.

Genetic advance as percentage of mean (GAM) was then calculated, to compare the extent of predicted genetic advance of different characters after standardization with their mean, according to the method suggested by Johnson *et al.* (1955). It was calculated as follow;

$$GAM = \frac{GA}{\bar{X}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

Where, \bar{X} stand for the population mean value of the character.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated among tree traits, namely number of capsules per tree, seeds/tree, seed length, seed breath, seed weight, 100-seed weight, and oil content, according to Yao and Mehlenbacher (2000). The correlation coefficient matrix and significance tests were calculated with Minitab 13 for Windows (Minitab, 2000).

Results and Discussion

Analysis of variance

Variability among the 18 families was estimated from a family-based estimation of mean, ranges, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation for each of the nine traits. Their estimated value is presented in Table 2. In addition to these parameters, the maximum and minimum measurements of these traits with their respective location, based on individual trees, are shown in Table 3.

The local population of physic nut was found to produce on average 210 capsules and 631 seeds per singletree. The number of seeds per tree varied between 192–1124 (Table 2). The maximum observations for all tree morphological traits were found at Kemise, and the minimum at Shewa Robit (Table 3). The mean values of seed length, seed breadth and seed thickness of

the local physic nut families from the study area were about 17.17 mm, 8.2 mm and 10.50 mm, respectively (Table2).

The average seed weight and 100-seed weight were about 0.60 g and 60.17 g (Table 2). The individual based seed weight and 100-seed weight varied between 0.35–0.8 g and 42–78 g, respectively (Table 2). The maximum values for seed weight traits were found at Shewa Robit (Table 3).

The oil content of the study population was on average 29.19% by weight for moisture-free seed. This varied from 22.40% at Chefa Robit to 34.40% at Shewa Robit (Table 2).

Table 2. Family-based estimate of mean, range, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation of traits

Traits	Ranges	Mean	SD	C.V%
No. branch/tree	16.00–54.00	35	9.62	27.72
No. capsule/tree	64.00–375.00	210	69.40	32.99
No. seed /tree	192.00–1124.00	631	208.20	33.00
Seed length (mm)	16.700–17.90	17.17	0.35	2.03
Seed breadth(mm)	7.90–8.60	8.21	0.23	2.78
Seed thickness(mm)	10.10–10.90	10.50	0.23	2.22
Seed weight (g)	0.53–0.71	0.60	0.05	8.03
100 seed wt(g)	52.53–70.16	60.17	4.89	8.14
Oil content (%)	22.40–34.40	29.19	2.26	7.75

Generally, the analysis of variance among 18 families of local physic nut for all traits showed significant differences ($p < 0.01$) at the minimum level. The ANOVA output for morphological and seed traits, as well as oil content, is shown in Table4. All of the tree morphological traits of the 18 families of the local physic nut population were different at ($p = 0.01$). The seed-size traits of the families were also significantly different. The 100-seed weight and oil content also differed highly significantly (Table 4).

Table 3. Observed value of each trait on individual sample trees

Traits	Min.	Location	Max.	Location
No. Branches/tree	2.80	Shewa Robit	84	Kemise
No. capsules/tree	27.80	Shewa Robit	534	Kemise
No. seeds /tree	83.00	Shewa Robit	1605	Kemise
Seed length (mm)	14.10	Senbete	19.0	Bati, Chefa Robit
Seed breadth (mm)	6.90	Harbu	9.5	Chefa Robit
Seed thickness (mm)	9.30	Kemise	11.3	Senbete
Seed weight (g)	0.35	Kemise	0.80	Shewa Robit
100-seed wt (g)	42.00	Chefa Robit	78.0	Shewa Robit
Oil content (%)	22.40	Chefa Robit	34.4	Shewa Robit

Table 4. Estimate of mean squares of families and error

Traits	Among families	Within family	Test	
	MSF	MSE	F Calc.	P Value
No. Branches/tree	8.12	3.4206	2.38**	0.003
No. capsules/tree	595.32	229.6718	2.59**	0.001
No. seeds /tree	1785.97	689.0153	2.59**	0.001
Seed length (mm)	0.0109	0.0054	2.02*	0.014
Seed breadth (mm)	0.0047	0.0025	1.88*	0.023
Seed thickness (mm)	0.0049	0.0016	3.06**	>0.0001
Seed weight (g)	0.0209	0.0069	3.03**	>0.0001
100-seed wt (g)	215.66	21.1770	10.18***	>0.0001
Oil content (%)	46.12	3.0627	15.06***	>0.0001

As was mentioned above, yield is a function of a number of traits, which directly or indirectly contribute to the overall yield of the crop. For the development of high-yielding varieties, a thorough knowledge of the existing genetic variation for yield and its components is required (Wani and Khan, 2006). For this reason, the investigation of tree morphological traits was designed so that they could be studied as a yield component.

The present study found that the local population of *J. curcas* exhibits considerable variation in all tree morphological traits. This indicates the presence of sufficient genetic variability for effective selection to identify superior genotypes.

The results were similar to those of other reports on *J. curcas* (Heller, 1996; Ginwal *et al.*, 2004; Pant *et al.*, 2006). These reports suggested that the causes of such variations in *J. curcas* were genetic and environmental influences. Among the 11 provenances of *J. curcas*, Heller (1996) found a significant difference in the number and weight of capsules per shrub, and the number and weight of seeds per shrub. Similarly, studies at Hisar, Bangalore, and Sardar Krushinagar in India revealed considerable variation in plant height, branches per plant and seed yield per plot (Heller, 1996). From these results, the genetic influences on the tree morphological traits of the species were inferred.

Another Indian study (Pant *et al.*, 2006) reported that the number of branches/tree, the number of fruits or capsules/tree and the number of seeds/tree differed significantly when tested over an altitudinal gradient. That study demonstrated the effect of site conditions on the variation exhibited by the species. Hence, variation in the present study might have arisen from either of the two causes.

Even if the trend and degree of variability were similar to those in other reports, the actual measured values were different. Evidently, the comparison of values from different germplasm, site conditions, age, and management is difficult, and the results seldom agree. Thus, it was difficult to compare the present study with other reports, because of the differences in estimation technique, growing conditions, age and definition of branch that were used. The present study was based on unselected, non-experimental units that are assumed to be older than five years but age; in the other literature, age was less than five years. Other reasons for the discrepancy in the mean values may be inherited variation, location variation, sampling error or random error. The present study was based entirely on a survey of domesticated, existing hedges and live fences, which had been planted for different purposes and under different conditions. However, the observed variability among the 18 families is indicative of genetic variability that could give a lead in the breeding of physic nut.

Study of the seed morphology of natural populations is often considered a useful step in the study of their genetic variability (Kaushik *et al.*, 2007). Seed

size and thickness differed significantly among families. The results for seed length, seed thickness, and seed breadth in the present study were similar to those in the Haryana population reported by Kaushik *et al.* (2007).

The 18 families were highly significantly different in 100-seed weight and oil content, indicating that the existing variation would allow selection for larger seed size and higher oil content. Kaushik *et al.* (2007) showed that there was significant variability for 100-seed weight and oil content among 24 accessions of physic nut from Haryana, India. Similarly, Ginwal *et al.* (2004) found that seed sources of physic nut varied significantly with respect to seed weight and oil content in whole seeds and in the kernel. Heller (1996) reported that the weight of seeds per shrub and 1000-seed weight were significant in Senegal.

The mean oil content, 28%, obtained in this study was lower compared to reported results elsewhere, *e.g.* Kaushik *et al.* (2007) 33%, Ginwal *et al.* (2004) 36%, and Sunil *et al.* (2007) 35–40%. This could derive from the fact that the present study was based on unselected non-experimental units, *i.e.* on relatively untended hedges, or be due to the inclusion of families with a low, oil content. On the other hand, the oil content is environmentally influenced, particularly by moisture and soil fertility.

In general, in view of the fact that the local population of *J. curcas* in eastern Amhara grows under varying site conditions, it might have experienced marked differences in selective pressure, or might have differed in its genetic background, in consequence of its hasty introduction. The observed variation confirms the potential of the local population of *Jatropha* to produce a high-yielding genetic material through selection.

Estimation of the Components of Variance

The estimates of genotypic, phenotypic, and environmental variances, together with the genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation of nine characters, are shown in Table 5.

Phenotypic and Genotypic Variances

Generally, Table 5 shows that the phenotypic variance was higher than the genotypic variance for all traits, however, the genotypic variance for 100-seed weight and oil content showed relatively little difference from the phenotypic variance. Phenotypic and environmental variances revealed that genotypic variances were high for 100-seed weight and oil content than the rest traits (Table 5). These two traits score higher for genotypic variance than for their

environmental variances, and slightly lower than for their phenotypic variation (Table 5). Genotypic and phenotypic variances were high for number of seeds per tree (121.884 and 810.899), and their minimum was for seed breadth (0.000256 and 0.003, respectively). Genotypic, environmental, and phenotypic variances of oil content were 4.784, 3.063 and 7.846, correspondingly (Table 5).

A tree-breeding strategy largely depends upon the extent of variability in the base population, which is measured by various parameters, viz. genotypic and phenotypic variances, and the genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation (Ginwal *et al.*, 2004). The higher phenotypic variances in all traits of the study, excluding 100-seed weight and seed oil content, indicated that a larger proportion of the phenotypic variance was contributed by the environmental variance. However, 100-seed weight and seed oil content traits had relatively greater genotypic than environmental variance. This implies that the performance of different sources of *J. curcas* for these traits can be tested with minimum cost and time. In support of this, Miller *et al.* (1957) noted that for those traits for which the genetic variance is larger relative to the environmental variance, accessions may be evaluated adequately by testing a few replicates, location and years. By contrast, they also suggested that traits with high environmental variances should be tested in a sufficient number of replications, years, and locations. The results obtained in the present study were similar to those reported by Ginwal *et al.* (2004).

In this study, the estimated genetic variance for all traits was smaller than the phenotypic, indicating that the observed variation was largely contributed by environmental variation of external factors, such as growing conditions, age, sampling error and random error. These might arise from the difference between the experimental units situated on different sites. On the other hand, the method used to partition the components of ANOVA was a simple linear model, which considered genetic variation as one factor and the cumulative external factors as error. So, the lower genetic variance does not imply that the genetic effect on the local population of physic nut is minimal absolutely, but as compared to the other cumulative non-genetic factors, including statistical errors, it was lower.

In general, high phenotypic and genotypic variances in the quantitative traits of the local population indicated better chances for selection to be successful.

Genotypic and Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation

The magnitude of genetic variation expressed by different tree morphological, seed size, seed weight and oil traits could be judged through the value of their respective coefficient of variation. In Figure. 2, it is shown that the magnitude of the *PCV* was higher than the corresponding genotypic ones for all characters. The overall variation in tree morphological traits were higher than the rest traits and seed size traits were found with the least range of variation, among the local families of physic nut in eastern Amhara. When a separate comparison of each trait considered, the highest *PCV* (35.76%) were resisted by two traits, i.e. number of seeds/tree and number of capsule and the least *PCV* (4.26%) was by seed thickness (Table 5). The genetic coefficient of variation values were between 1.81% (seed thickness) and 14.88% (number of seeds/tree). The *GCV* and *PCV* value for oil content were 7.94% and 9.6%. Generally, the difference between the *PCV* and *GCV* of oil content was lowest, followed by 100-seed weight, and the maximum value of this difference was observed on seed breadth.

The genotypic coefficient of variation measures the range of genetic variability shown by the plant trait, and helps to compare the genetic variability present in various traits. The observed difference in the magnitude of variation within a given trait might arise from different reason. Regarding the tree morphological traits, the high level of variation might arise from the a exposure and nature of the traits to human or environmental effects, as mentioned above the study material was based on already existing farmer's hedge which grow under different management and growing conditions.

In this study, the genotypic coefficients of variation are comparatively lower than phenotypic coefficient of variation for all the traits. Similar result were reported by Ginwal *et al.* (2004), for the number of branch/tree, seed weight traits and oil content of local physic nut of India. The except for oil content, the result of this study on seed size and weight trait is in agreement with the results of Kaushik *et al.* (2007). The *PCV* and *GCV* oil content of that study was reported as equal which deny the effect of environment on that trait, this could arise either the statistical model used for partitioning the components of variances during analysis of variances or the efficiency of the oil extraction technique used in the experiment.

Table 5. Genotypic, environmental, phenotypic variances and genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation in 18 families of physic nut

Traits	Variances			CV %	
	V_g	V_e	V_p	GCV	PCV
No. of branches/tree	0.52	3.42	3.94	13.02	35.76
No. of capsules/tree	40.63	229.67	270.30	14.88	38.37
No. of seeds /tree	121.88	689.02	810.90	14.87	38.37
Seed length (mm)	0.001	0.0050	0.006	1.84	4.51
Seed breadth (mm)	0.0003	0.0025	0.003	1.95	6.68
Seed thickness (mm)	0.00036	0.0019	0.002	1.81	4.26
Seed weight (g)	0.002	0.007	0.008	7.41	14.81
100-seed wt (g)	21.609	21.177	42.786	7.73	10.88
Oil content (%)	4.784	3.063	7.846	7.49	9.60

Figure 2. Graphical presentation of the GCV and PCV of nine traits of local *Jatropha curcas* families.

Genetic Parameters

Heritability

The genetic coefficient of variation provides information on the genetic variability present in various quantitative characters, but it is not possible to determine the amount of the variation that was heritable from only the genotypic coefficient of variation. The genetic coefficient of variation, together

with heritability estimates, would give the best picture of the amount of advance to be expected from selection (Burton, 1952). Thus, the heritable portion of the variation was elucidated with the help of heritability estimates.

The broad-sense heritability estimates of all traits of the study were from moderate to high. Among the nine traits, the broad-sense heritability (h^2) was highest (0.93) for oil content, followed by 100-seed weight (0.90), and the lowest recorded was for seed thickness (0.47) (Table 6). Heritability is described as an important tool in selecting superior phenotypes (plus trees), based on the phenotypic performance of quantitative characters (Vasudeva *et al.*, 2004). Heritability is considered to be high when the value is between 0.70–0.99 and moderate when it is 0.4–0.7 (Gomes *et al.*, 2003), coefficients of variation in 18 families of physic nut. A similar report of higher heritability for 100-seed weight and oil content was presented by Kaushik *et al.* (2007).

If the heritability of a character is very high (> 80%), selection for such a character should be fairly, easy owing to the close correspondence between the genotypes and the phenotypes which arises from a relatively smaller contribution of the environment to the phenotype (Singh, 1999). For a character with low heritability (< 40%); however, selection may be considerably more difficult or virtually impractical, owing to the masking effect of environment on the genotypic effects (Singh, 1990). Depending on this fact, in the present study, it can be safely concluded that the selection of genotypes based on 100-seed weight and oil content would be more satisfactory in the case of physic nut.

Genetic Advance

To predict the selection effects precisely, heritability accompanied with genetic advance is more useful than heritability alone (Johnson *et al.*, 1955). Therefore, genetic advance was also computed as percentage of mean, to predict the gain from a selection of superior genotypes from the local population of physic nut, assuming for 5% selection intensity. The results (Table 6) indicated that maximum genetic advance as percentage of mean of 48.45% followed by 48.44% was recorded in number of seeds/tree and number of capsule/tree, respectively. The minimum of 4.67% genetic advance as percentage of mean was obtained for seed length. Oil content had a promise of 18% of gain over the mean.

The ultimate aim of most variability or screening studies is to provide a framework for future selection; the present study therefore also attempted to provide the probable genetic gain, for future selection is to be conducted on the population. Johnson *et al.* (1955) indicated that the estimate of heritability and genetic advance should always be considered simultaneously, because high heritability is not always associated with high genetic advance. The utility of heritability estimates increases when they are used in conjunction with genetic advance, expressed as a percentage of the mean (Johnson *et al.*, 1955; Allard, 1960). As Panes (1957), when there is high genetic advance coupled with high to moderate heritability would give better scope for selection. In addition, the author noted that, the association of high heritability with high genetic advance is due to additive gene effect.

In the present study, moderate heritability of the numbers of branches/tree, the number of capsules/tree and the number of seeds/tree (Table 6) coupled with high genetic advance indicates the presence of additive gene effects. This result was in agreement with the result of Ginwal *et al.* (2004) on tree growth traits of different physic nut seed in central India. This type of genetic effect and the wide range of variation of tree morphological traits of local physic nut population offer good scope for genetic improvement of this species and their improvement can be done through mass selection.

Next to above the traits, 100 seed weight have shown relatively high genetic *GAM* (20.17%) but higher heritability (90%) than those traits. This has clearly shown that a considerable portion of variance of the trait is additive. This signifies that these traits are under strong genetic control and good amount of heritable additive genetic component can be exploited for further selection. A similar report of higher heritability and *GAM* for seed weight trait was presented by Ali *et al.* (2003).

Although, the highest heritability (93%) was computed for the seed oil content, its *GAM* (< 20%) was relatively lower than the tree morphological and seed weight traits, high heritability and again than the above mentioned traits. In general sense, high heritability (broad-sense) may be due to non-additive gene action, however, it shall be reliable only if accompanied by high genetic gain (Rawat and Nautiyal, 2007). For this reason, a selection based on this trait may not provide with an improved performance of progenies.

In the other side, the seed size traits revealed with very low *GAM* of 4.68–6.43% (Table 6). So that the traits are not expected to show high genetic

advance and it can be judged to have more of non-additive genetic effects than additive genetic effects (Roy *et al.*, 2004). A moderate heritability for characters, combined with low *GCV* and genetic advance as percent of mean indicates the importance of both additive and non-additive gene action for these characters (Paulsamy *et al.*, 2007).

In general, the findings of the present investigation on the genetic advance of seed size traits and seed oil content of physic nut are in congruous with that of Kaushik *et al.* (2007).

Table 6. Heritability, genetic advance, and genetic advance as a percentage of the mean for 18 physic nut families

Traits	h^2	GA	GAM
No. of branches/tree	0.58	2.36	42.58
No. of capsules/tree	0.61	20.76	48.44
No. of seeds /tree	0.61	35.96	48.45
Seed length (mm)	0.50	0.08	4.68
Seed breadth (mm)	0.47	0.05	6.43
Seed thickness (mm)	0.67	0.06	5.90
Seed weight (g)	0.67	0.12	20.40
100-seed wt (g)	0.90	12.13	20.17
Oil content (%)	0.93	5.38	18.42

Coefficients of Phenotypic Correlation

The Pearson correlation coefficients (r) among tree morphological, seed-size, seed-weight, and oil traits with their level of significance are presented in Table 7. There was a high correlation among tree morphological traits, with a high significance level. There was no significant correlation between tree morphological traits and all seed traits. All seed-size traits were very highly significant and positively correlated with seed weight and 100-seed weight. The oil content had a highly significant correlation with 100-seed weight, and the test showed that it had no significant correlation with seed breadth alone. The correlation between 100-seed weight, all seed-size and seed-weight traits was very highly significant.

The seed breadth was correlated significantly with all seed-size and seed-weight traits. Seed weight was correlated highly significantly with all seed-size traits and seed weight, with high correlation coefficients. It had also a highly significant correlation with oil content with a moderate 'r'. There were no

significant correlations between oil content and the number of capsules/tree, the number of seeds/tree and seed breadth. The correlation between oil content and seed-weight traits was highly significant, with moderate strength. The 100-seed weight had the largest positive correlation with oil content, with very high significance, followed by seed weight with oil content.

The nature of inter-trait correlations may enhance or retard the selection progress. Therefore, analysis of the correlation between yield and yield components is essential in determining the selection criteria (Yücel *et al.*, 2006). As oil production is the prime goal of physic nut cultivation, at least for the current period, any trait that will maximize oil yield is of primary concern on tree improvement work on this species.

Oil content/seed is a direct contributor to the overall oil yield of the crop. In the present study, the oil content had a highly significant, positive correlation with seed weight ($r = 0.315$) and 100-seed weight ($r = 0.463$). A similar result was reported by Kaushik *et al.* (2007) regarding the correlation between seed weight and oil content. Larger seeds in castor, rapeseed, linseed and niger result in a higher oil content from a similar genetic background (Getinet and Nigussie, 1997; Getinet *et al.*, 2008). This indicated that selection for larger seed size or weight would lead to higher oil content. This is because large seeds have a relatively higher amount of embryo and endosperm where oil is deposited, as compared to smaller seeds.

In addition, a significant positive correlation was found for the trait oil content, with seed thickness and seed length. As regards the correlation between seed length and seed oil content, a significant negative correlation has been reported, which is the opposite of the results of the current study. The present paper cannot explain the reason for this contradiction, other than in terms of statistical error. Rather, the correlation with oil content was non-significant and very weak; surprisingly, the results of Kaushik *et al.* (2007) are similar.

In general, tree morphological traits were not correlated with all seed traits, and showed a significant, negative correlation with the number of branches/tree and oil content. This might be a result of competition for nutrients and photosynthates between vegetative growth and the production of additional seed, as the number of branches increases.

Table 7. Estimate of Phenotypic Correlation coefficients

Traits	No. Branches /tree	No. Capsules/tree	No. Seeds/tree	Seed Length	Seed Breadth	Seed Thickness	Seed weight	100-seed Wt.
No. capsules /tree	0.777***							
P-value	<0.0001							
No. seeds /tree	0.777***	0.999***						
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001						
Seed length	0.026	0.049	0.049					
P-value	0.740	0.534	0.534					
Seed breadth	0.093	0.143	0.143	0.506***				
P-value	0.241	0.069	0.069	<0.0001				
Seed thickness	-0.009	0.113	0.113	0.471***	0.444**			
P-value	0.911	0.154	0.154	<0.0001	<0.0001			
Seed weight	0.031	0.062	0.062	0.661***	0.617***	0.563**		
P-value	0.697	0.433	0.433	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001		
100-seed wt	-0.059	0.039	0.039	0.343***	0.331***	0.35***	0.576***	
P-value	0.456	0.619	0.619	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	
Oil %	-0.227*	-0.116	-0.116	0.154*	0.099	0.161*	0.315***	0.463***
P-value	0.004	0.141	0.141	0.050	0.212	0.040	<0.0001	<0.0001

Significant, ** highly significant, and *** very highly significant.

Conclusion

The existing population of physic nut exhibits a considerable degree of variation among families or sub-populations grown at different sites in Eastern Amhara. The larger variation between families than within families in this study, leads to the conclusion that there is a good opportunity for selection and breeding among physic nut populations.

The values and measurements observed in this study for seed weight and oil content were relatively lower than reported elsewhere, probably due to environmental effects. The samples were taken from hedges, not from experimental plots or commercial plantations; hence, the lower values are not too surprising. Nevertheless, the range of oil content observed in this study is sufficient to initiate selection of superior genotype with maximum seed oil content.

On the other hand, the heritability of most characters was moderate, except for oil content and seed weight. The heritability observed for oil content and seed weight was comparable with available reports on the same spices and much higher than those reported elsewhere in other oilseeds. The higher heritability of oil content and seed weight may indicate that selection for oil content could be successful. However, this was not substantiated by the higher value of genetic advance as a percentage of the mean. Therefore, direct selection for oil content may be difficult and even impossible, as is known from other oilseeds. Fortunately, one of the most economically valuable traits, oil content, was highly and positively correlated with seed size and weight, so that a selection for larger seed size and weight can result in higher oil contents. This type of indirect selection is also observed other oil seed bearing species like *Ricinus communis*, *Helianthus annuus*, *Brassica napus*, and *Nigella sativa*.

Oil production is the most important goal of physic nut cultivation; the economics of the production is also determined by seed yield equivalent to oil content of a planting material. The seed yield of physic nut depends on the number of female flowers/tree, so, during selecting genotype for commercial plantation, this type of trait should be considered in addition to the oil content.

The observed variation in tree and seed traits and oil content is very encouraging for the selection of high-yielding provenances of physic nut for future plantation. Physic nut is non-edible, is adapted to marginal lands and hence does not compete with food production, which makes it an excellent

candidate for biodiesel. However, higher economic yields, both in seed and oil content, are important. Therefore, the selection of high-yielding provenances, with oil contents of well over 40%, is required before any commercial plantation is initiated.

References

- Augustus, G., Jayabalan, M. and Seiler, G, 2002. Evaluation and Bio Induction Of Energy Components of *Jatropha curcas*. *Biomass and Bioenergy*. 23/3:161–16.
- Abney, M., McPeck, M. S. and Ober, C, 2000. Estimation of Variance Components of Quantitative Traits in Inbred Populations. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 66: 629–650.
- Adolph, S. C. and Hardin, J. S, 2006. Estimating Phenotypic Correlations: Correcting for Bias Due to Intra-individual Variability. *Functional Ecology*. 21:178–184.
- Allard, R. W. and Hansche, P. E, 1964. Some Parameters of Population Variability and Their Implication in Plant Breeding. In: A.G. Norman (ed). Academic press, New York. *Advances in agronomy*. 16: 281–282.
- Allard, R.W, 1960. *Principles of Plant Breeding*. John Willy and Sons., inc. New York. 485 pp.
- Ali, N., Javidfar, F., Elmira, J. Y. and Mirza, M. Y, 2003. Relationship among Yield Components and Selection Criteria for Yield Improvement in Winter Rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.). *Pak. J. Bot.* 35/2: 167–174.
- Aliyu, O. M, 2006. Phenotypic Correlation and Path Coefficient Analysis of Nut Yield and Yield Components in Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* L.). *Silvae Genetica*. 55/1: 19–24.
- Benge, M, 2006. Assessment of the potential of *Jatropha Curcas*, (Biodiesel tree) for energy production and other uses in developing countries. (http://www.echotech.org/mambo/index.php?option=com_docman&task=doc_view&id=179&Itemid=68). (Posted on ECHO's website with permission of the author on July 2006 and updated August 2006). (Accessed on 11-May-08).
- Burton, G.W, 1952. Quantitative Inheritance in Grasses. In: *Proceeding of the sixth International Grass Congress*. 1: 277.
- Degefa Tolossa, 2001. *Causes of Seasonal Food Insecurity in Oromiya Zone of Amhara Region: Farmers' View*. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Contemporary Development Issues in Ethiopia*. Western Michigan University, Kalamazoo, Michigan. <http://homepages.wmich.edu/~asefa/Conference%20and%20Seminar/Papers/2001%20papers/Paper119.pdf>. (Accessed on 11-May-08).
- Dhanai, C. S., Uniyal, A. K. and Todaria, N. P, 2003. Source Variation in *Albizia chinensis* (Osbeck) Mer.; Seed and Seedling Characteristics. *Silvae Genetica*. 52/ 5-6: 259–266.
- Getinet Alemaw and Nigussie Alemayehu. 1996. Highland oil crops; A three decade of research experience, Research Report 30. EIAR Addis Abeba.
- Getinet Alemaw, Daniel Bistrat and Frew Kelemu, 2008. Opportunities and challenges of oilseed production as sources of biodiesel in Ethiopia. In: *Proceedings of the First Biodiesel Workshop in Ethiopia*. (In press).
- Ginwal, H. S., Rawat, P. S. and Srivastava, R. L, 2004. Seed source variation in growth performance and oil yield of *Jatropha curcas* Linn. in Central India. Division of Genetics and Tree Propagation. Forest Research Institute. India.

- Gomes, R. L. F., Vello, N. A. and Filho, J. A. A, 2004. Genetic Analysis of F6 and F6:7 Soybean Generations. Brazilian Society of Plant Breeding. Crop Breeding and Applied Biotechnology. 4: 35-42.
- Gomez, K. A. and Gomez, A. A, 1984. Statistical procedures for agricultural research. 2nd ed. John Willy and Sons., inc., New York, pp.680.
- Heller, J, 1996. Physic nut. *Jatropha curcas* L. Promoting the conservation and use of underutilized and neglected crops. 1. Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research, Gatersleben/ International Plant Genetic Resources Institute, Rome.
- Henning, R, 1996. Combating desertification: The *Jatropha* Project of Mali , West Africa. Arid Land Newsletter. No.40.
- Hallauer, A.R, 2007. History, contribution, and future of quantitative genetics in plant Breeding: Lessons From Maize.In: International Plant Breeding Symposium. USA. Crop Sci. 47:4-19.
- Jessen, R, 1955. Determining the fruit count on a tree by randomized branch sampling. BIOMETRICS. 11/1: 99-109.
- Jones, N. and Miller, J. H,1992. *Jatropha curcas*: A multipurpose species for problematic sites. Land resources series No.1 Asia Technical Department. World Bank. Washington.
- Johnson, H.W., Robinson , H.F. and Comstock, R.E,1955. Estimates of genetic and environmental variability in soybeans. Agron. J. 47: 314–318.
- Kaushik, N., Kumar, K., Kumar, S., Kaushik, N. and Roy, S, 2007. Genetic variability and divergence studies in seed traits and oil content of *Jatropha (Jatropha curcas* L.) Accessions. Biomass and Bioenergy. 31/7: 497–502.
- Kumar, S., Dungey, H. S. and Matheson, A. C, 2006. Genetic parameters and strategies for genetic improvement of stiffness in radiata pine. Silvae Genetica. 55/2: 77–84.
- Kung, F.H. and Bey, C.F, 1978. Heritability construction for provenance and family selection. Proc. lake states for tree improve conf. 13: 136–46.
- Lynch, M, 1999. Estimating genetic correlations in natural populations. Genet Res., Camb. 74: 255–264.
- Makkar H. P. S., Becker, K. and Schmook, B. 2002. Edible provenances of *Jatropha curcas* from quintana roo state of mexico and effect of roasting on anti nutrient and toxic factors in seeds. <http://www.jatropha.de/schmook1.htm/>. (last modification 16.08.02). (Accessed on 1-May-08).
- Mendoza T., Castillo, E. and Aquino, A, 2007a. Towards making *Jatropha* “Tubang Bakod” a viable source of biodiesel in the Philippines. http://www.relocalize.net/towards_making_jatropha_tubang_bakod_a_viable_source_of_biodiesel_in_the_philippines.
- Mendoza, T., Zamora, O. and Lales, J, 2007b. *Jatropha curcas*: What the public should know. (Unpublished). http://www.relocalize.net/jatropha_what_the_public_should_know. (Available Online on Fri, 24-08-2007). (Accessed on 1-May-08).
- Mahadevan, N. P., Sivakumar, V. and Singh, B, 1999. Relationship of cone and seed traits on progeny growth performance in casuarina equisetifolia, Forst. and Forst.f. Silvae Genetica. 48/6: 273-277
- Ministry of Energy and Mines, 2007. The national bio-energy strategy. Addis Ababa.
- Minitab, Inc, 2000. Minitab statistical software. Release 13 for windows (computer program). Minitab, Inc., State College, Penn.
- MoA/FAO, 1984. Land-use and land cover map of Ethiopia, 1: 1,000,000, A.A.
- Panes, V. G, 1957. Genetics of quantitative characters in relation to plant breeding. Indian J. Genet. 17: 318–328.

- Pant, K.S., Khosla, V., Kumar, D. and Gairola, S, 2006. Seed oil content variation in *Jatropha Curcas* (L), in Different Altitudinal Ranges and Site Conditions, in H.P India. <http://www.lyonia.org/downloadPDF.php?pdfID=390.487.1>. (Accessed on 1-May-08).
- Paulsamy, S., Vijayakumar, K. K. and Ram, G. S, 2007. Genetic variations and degree of correlation in four ecological variants of *Gaultheria fragrantissima* (Wallich.) in Nilgiri Biosphere Reserve, Western Ghats, India. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 6/5: 501–503. ISSN 1684–5315.
- Poehlman, J. M. and Sleper, D.A, 1995. *Breeding field crops*. 4th edition. Iowa State Press. A Blackwell publishing company.
- Rawat, R. S. and Nautiyal, S, 2007. Genotype-site interactions in growth, physiological and biochemical parameters in clones of *Dalbergia sissoo* Roxb. *Silvae Genetica*. 56/5: 201–206.
- Roy, S. M., Thapliyal, R. C. and Phartyal, S. S, 2004. Seed source variation in cone, seed and seedling characteristic across the natural distribution of Himalayan low level *pine Pinus roxburghii* (Sarg). *Silvae Genetica*. 53/3: 116–123.
- Seegeler C. J. P, 1983. *Oil plants in Ethiopia: Their taxonomy and agricultural significance*. PhD Thesis, Wageningen University, Pudoc, Wageningen. The Netherlands,
- Singh, B.D, 1990. *Plant breeding*. Kalyani Publishers, New Delhi, India. 458 pp.
- Sunil, N., Varaprasad, K., Sivaraj, N., Kumar, T., Abraham, B. and Prasad, R, 2007. Assessing *Jatropha curcas* L. germplasm in-situ—A case study. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, In Press, Corrected Proof.
- Thongbai, P., O'Donnell, A. G, Wood, D. and Syers, J. K, 2006. *Biofuels Research and Development at Mae Fah Luang University*. In: *The 2nd Joint International Conference on "Sustainable Energy and Environment (SEE 2006)"*. Bangkok, Thailand.
- Vasudeva, R., Hanumantha, M. and Gunaga, R. P, 2004. Genetic variation for floral traits among Teak (*Tectona grandis* Linn. f.) Clones: Implications to seed Orchard Fertility. *Current Science*. 87/3: 358–362.
- Vavilov, I, 1951. *The origin, variation, immunity breeding of cultivated plants*. Translated from the Russian by Chester, K.S. Ronald Press Co., New York.. 37–38 pp.
- Walsh, B. J, 2007. *Basic designs for estimation of genetic parameters*. University of Arizona. <http://nitro.biosci.arizona.edu/courses/EEB519A-2007/Lecture05.pdf>. (Accessed on 18-Apr-08).
- Wani, M. R. and Khan, S, 2006. Estimates of genetic variability in mutated populations and the scope of selection for yield attributes in *Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek. *Egyptian Journal of Biology*. 8:1-6
- Wiesenhütter, J, 2003. *Use of the Physic Nut (Jatropha curcas L.) to combat desertification and reduce poverty*. Possibilities and limitations of technical solutions in a particular socio-economic environment, the case of Cape Verde. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit (GTZ). Convention Project to Combat Desertification (CCD Project). Bonn, Germany.
- World Bank, 2002. *The use of Jatropha curcas oil as raw material and fuel*. Using the Indigenous Knowledge of Jatropha. No. 47.
- Yang, J. C. and Chiu, C. M, 2006. Genetic Variation of Wood Specific Gravity and Tracheid Length of Open-Pollinated Progeny Families in *Calocedrus formosana*. *Taiwan J For Sci*. 21/3: 305–15.
- Yao, Q. and Mehlenbacher, S. A, 2000. Heritability, variance components and correlation of morphological and phenological traits in Hazelnut. *Plant Breeding*. 119: 369–381.

Yücel, D.Z., Anlarsal, A. E. and Yücel, C, 2006. Genetic variability, correlation and path analysis of yield and yield components in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). Turk J Agric For. 30: 183–188.

Zobel B. and Talbert, J, 1984. Applied forest tree improvement. New York: Wiley. 505 pp.

Additional web sites reference

Jatropha World. Centre for Jatropha Promotion and Biodiesel. Cultivation technology. <http://www.jatrophaworld.org/10.html>. (accessed on 16-Apr-08).

Jatropha curcas L. in Africa. Global facilitation unit for underutilized species. By Henning, Reinhard K. Rothkreuz 11, D-88138 Weissenberg, Gemany. http://www.underutilized-species.org/Documents/PUBLICATIONS/jatropha_curcas_africa.pdf. (Accessed on 16-Apr-08).

BioKing. Jatropha plantation investment and opportunity. <http://www.bioking.nl/jatropha/biodieselinvestment.htm>. (Accessed on 16-Apr-08).

Wikipedia, the free online encyclopedia (<http://en.wikipedia.org>)

Annex 1. List of family mean, LSD and mean comparing prefixes

Location	Family	No.branches /tree		No.capsules /tree		No.Seeds /tree		SL		SB		ST		SWt.		100-SWt.		Oil%	
Shewa Robit	SR01	16	a	64	a	192	a	17.4	bcd	8.1	abcde	10.5	abcdef	0.61	bcde	60.67	degh	31.7	ijk
Shewa Robit	SR02	28	abcd	193	bcd	579	bcd	17.9	d	8.4	bcde	10.9	g	0.71	f	70.16	j	32.8	k
Shewa Robit	SR03	35	bcde	220	bcd	659	bcd	17.6	cd	8.4	cde	10.7	efg	0.67	ef	66.36	ij	31.8	jk
Senbete	SB01	35	bcde	186	bc	559	bc	17.3	abcd	8.5	e	10.6	cdefg	0.63	bcde	62.78	fghi	27.3	b
Senbete	SB02	19	ab	161	abc	483	abc	17.3	abcd	8.2	abcde	10.7	efg	0.60	abcde	60.41	degh	31.5	hijk
Senbete	SB03	37	cdef	262	bcde	786	bcd	17.0	abc	8.3	abcde	10.8	fg	0.64	cdef	64.15	ghi	29.7	efg
Chefa Robit	CR01	45	def	175	abc	526	abc	16.7	a	8.1	abcd	10.1	a	0.53	a	52.84	a	27.6	bc
Chefa Robit	CR02	40	cdef	208	bcd	622	bcd	16.9	abc	8.2	abcde	10.3	abcde	0.57	abc	56.15	abc	24.8	a
Chefa Robit	CR03	34	bcde	204	bcd	613	bcd	17.1	abc	8.2	abcde	10.7	efg	0.60	abcde	59.28	cdef	30.7	ghij
Kemise	K01	43	cdef	281	cde	842	cde	17.5	cd	8.6	e	10.5	abcdefg	0.64	cdef	64.90	hi	30.0	fgh
Kemise	K02	36	bcdef	222	bcd	665	bcd	17.3	abcd	7.9	abc	10.2	abcd	0.57	abc	56.67	abcd	26.9	b
Kemise	K03	54	f	375	e	1124	e	17.6	cd	8.5	de	10.7	efg	0.66	def	65.76	i	29.0	cdef
Harbu	H01	28	abcd	181	abc	541	abc	16.7	a	8.1	abcd	10.3	abcd	0.59	abcd	59.01	cdef	30.8	ghijk
Harbu	H02	49	ef	312	de	937	de	16.8	ab	8.1	abcd	10.2	ab	0.57	abc	57.71	bcde	28.4	bcde
Harbu	H03	34	bcde	259	bcde	776	bcd	17.3	abcd	8.5	de	10.7	efg	0.62	bcde	61.46	efgh	30.1	fghi
Bati	B01	27	abc	152	ab	457	ab	16.7	a	7.9	a	10.4	abcde	0.58	abcd	57.22	bcde	29.3	defg
Bati	B02	31	abcde	163	abc	490	abc	16.8	ab	7.9	ab	10.2	abc	0.56	ab	54.39	ab	27.8	bcd
Bati	B03	32	abcde	168	abc	504	abc	17.2	abcd	7.9	a	10.5	bcdefg	0.53	a	52.53	a	25.2	a
mean		35±20.76		210±141.2		631±423.7		17.2±0.8		8.2±0.5		10.5±0.439		0.6±0.09		60.1±6.46		29.2±2.76	
LSD		18		121		363		0.7		0.5		0.4		0.08		4.25		1.6	